

SPECIFICITY OF THE LOWER LIMBS INJURIES IN FOOTBALL AND HANDBALL

Marta Nitka, Agata Niewiadomska-Matuła, Agata Król

Jagiellonian University Medical College-Institute of Physiotherapy, Krakow, Poland

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Summary

During the whole life human body is exposed to diverse strains which are associated with the natural need for movement, improvement of the physical fitness or as in case of football and handball players with so called 'sport exploitation'.

The competitors very often achieve their results at the cost of their own health. Their whole body and particularly their movement apparatus is exposed to hard and exhausting work during trainings and matches. They exploit their bodies to the maximum and their bodies need adequate time to regenerate and adapt for new phenomena. Sports injuries in team games are not only the consequence of the direct contact of the players, but also wrongly carried out warm-up, lack of warm-up or even exercises which are harmful to the movement apparatus.

The thesis presents the descriptive analysis of the lower limbs injuries.

Presented material is an attempt to show whether football and handball players are vulnerable to lower limbs injuries, how these injuries differ in location and what their kinds are. Thanks to the research we can provide evidence that in both sports lower limbs injuries occur very often and they are part and parcel of these sports disciplines.

It is often omitted that sportsmen continue the game despite the pain which is the signal to stop the effort. It also happens that players who have experienced injuries, for the first time or due to the reinjury, get back to trainings as soon as possible ignoring the time required for full recovery.

In contemporary world, new methods are used to diagnose and choose the proper therapy. Along with better surgical techniques and rehabilitation they allow to improve the health protection of the sportsmen and reduce the number of injuries in sport. Prevention is a very important element of every sport also football and handball. It can reduce the frequency of injuries which happen to sportsmen. Coaches, sports medicine doctors and physiotherapists should play an important role in these actions. They should not approve of the excessive strains of the sportsmen's bodies, they should also prevent unfortunate accidents.

Introduction

One of the elements of the healthy life style and spending free time is physical activity. This resulted in rapidly growing interest in regular training, systematic physical exercises and different disciplines of sport. Unfortunately, alongside positive aspects of physical activity of a sport nature, injuries seem to be inseparable from it. Among all the team disciplines pursued by general public, football seems to be at the forefront of those the most popular, but also the most traumatic sports. Also very popular handball, contrary to its name, brings more injuries to the lower limbs. Both football and handball, owing to their contact nature, which results from direct competition (and often intentional fouls), are counted as the most dangerous sport disciplines, and players are exposed to numerous sport injuries both during training or warm-up and play.

The injuries in the competitive sport are specific. The sportsmen, who are set up to score and win, in order to get better and better results, try to cover up for minor, as they believe, injuries, and also overlook time necessary for full recovery after the injury.

The term "sport related injury" describes all kinds of injuries that occur during sporting activities. It has been defined in various ways:

1. European Council defined a sport injury as a result of actively participating in sporting activity, which makes physical effort impossible, requires medical assistance and has economic consequences. (Adamczyk 2005).

2. Widuchowski describes a sport injury as the injury which occurs while practising a physical activity of a sport nature, both during training and matches. It contributes to numerous disabilities, which in their turn can eliminate from being physically active either temporarily, or for good. (Widuchowski, Grzywocz 1996).

3. In the article by W. Siwek, injury has been defined as an accident which results in minimum one day's absence from training. According to American national register, injuries are classified as: light (1-7 days), moderate (8-21 days) and bad (over 21 days) of being excluded from actively pursuing sport.

Lower limb injuries account for 80% of all accidents that happen during playing football. They can be classified according to: the place, tissue healing time and the incidence of the symptoms characteristic for the specific injury.

J. Widuchowski put forward the following classification:

1. distortions and sprains of joints
2. musculotendinous injuries (sprains, tears, ruptures)
3. micro-injuries: (contusions, sprains, tears, cuts)

4. bone fractures
5. infections
6. inflammations.(Widuchowski , Grzywocz 1996).

From the work we learn that the most frequent injuries in football were those of knee joint, most precisely, knee ligaments. At football, damages to both anterior cruciate ligament (ACL) and posterior cruciate ligament (PCL) occur. Anterior cruciate ligament (ACL) and posterior cruciate ligament (PCL) go exactly in the center of the knee joint where they cross, which accounts for the term “cruciate”. (Mędraś 2004).

Anterior cruciate ligament (ACL) gets damaged following the femur being pushed backwards. ACL tear is often connected with the specific direct or torsion injury. The player feels intensive pain, and the swelling builds up for 6-24 hours.

When hematoma is present, the intra-articular fracture might be suspected. But when the swelling is not big and the knee returns to its function thanks to the effective and normal compensation processes, the player might not be aware of the danger. The joint working incorrectly wears much more quickly. The remittent exudation to the knee joint may appear, also knee retraction and muscular atrophy are possible. They may be accompanied with meniscus and cartilage damage leading to the knee lock and the degenerative changes. (www.carolina.pl). ACL damage is “the beginning of an end to the knee”.

Figure 1. Normal and torn anterior cruciate ligament as seen during arthroscopy. Source: www.carolina.pl

When the anterior cruciate ligament tear has been confirmed, the treatment involves reconstruction using arthroscopic methods, during which the damaged ligament is replaced by the autogenous grafts of the tendons taken from the patient (the looped semi-tendon, gracilis muscle tendon, patellar tendon, aponeurosis of the rectus femoris tendon). Straight after the surgery, the patient is submitted to intensive and specialistic rehabilitation aiming at retaining full operability of the joint and getting the control over it, bringing back proper muscular strength, the coordination of movements and the functions of the extremity. It is also important for the sportsman to get back their confidence and trust as regards its effectiveness. (Andrzejewski, Trytek- Piskiewicz 2004), (Frańczuk i wsp.2004), (Pasierbiński, Jarzabek 2002), (Trzaska 2002).

The elements of improvement from the kinesiotherapy area are exercises both in close and open kinematic chains. Relief, postisometric relaxation of muscle ischiopublic crus and quadriceps exercises are applied. The femoral nerve neuroimmobilization is performed. Also swimming pool exercises can also be used.(Pasierbiński, Jarzabek 2002). It is important to remember that between 6-th and 12-th month after the surgery, cruciate ligament reconstruction process is very rapid and during this time the ligament’s durability is limited.(Milewska, Mańka 2002), (Pasierbiński, Jarzabek 2002).

The damage to the posterior cruciate ligament happens much more rarely with footballers, and it is caused by the force, which displaces the shin backwards with the knee joint being bent. This happens when the football player lands on his bent knee during hyperextension injuries. The main symptom of discontinuity in the ligament is the sensation of instability, especially at the final phase of the snap. There may be pain of the medial part and of patello-femoral joint. In contrast to the anterior cruciate ligament damage, with the posterior one, clunking of the joint doesn’t occur.(Brown 2006), (www.kulturystka.magicsport.pl). In most cases, non operational treatment is recommended, in particular an intensive quadriceps rehabilitation. When

other methods fail, ligament reconstruction is applied.(Brown 2006).

During rehabilitation, mostly straightening exercises, which are used in the closed kinematic chain, are applied. The rehabilitation exercises include squats, bicycle riding, stepper running and lower limb stretching. They usually last for 3-6 weeks, and after the rehabilitation process, the use of knee joint stabilizers, especially those with adjustable bending angle capability is recommended. (Górecki 1997), (Heim , Baltensweiler 1995).

From the results of the work being discussed we can assume that the knee joint seems to be the place of the most frequent injuries at handball, and exactly excessive inversion, popularly referred to as “twisted ankle”. This injury may occur at incorrect landing, the twist on the foot, and also during running along uneven surface. The injuries resulting from excessive eversion or direct injury are rare. Depending on the severity of the injury we can distinguish three levels of the lateral ankle distorsion (Paterka 2001):

- The first level is characterized by the tear or strain of the ligaments. Slight pain, swelling and limitation of joint mobility appear, but instability is not present.
- The second level is characterized by partial tear of the ligament fibers, positive anterior drawer sign appears. The pain, huge swelling and obvious immobility are present.
- The third level means rupture of the ligament fibers, anterior drawer sign and the symptoms of the subluxation of the ankle in fork tibia fibular. There is substantial swelling and pain (www.carolina.pl), (www.medisa.pl).

Figure 2. The levels of the ligament damage.

Level 1 – the sprain of the ligaments

Level 2 – partial damage to the ligaments

Level 3 – the rupture of the ligaments

Source: www.carolina.pl

The distortion I° requires physical activity limitation for 7-10 days until the swelling and pain stop. It is beneficial to use the cold, modeling dressing until the swelling disappears (i.e. horse-shoe shaped pelota or pneumatic stabilizer).

The distortion II° requires offloading of the limb in the preliminary period, its stabilization

in the gypsum scale or orthosis for 10-14 days. It is possible to resume training after 3 weeks.

The distortion III° requires longer immobilization, usually in a stabilizer for approximately 4 week. The physiotherapy applied is anti-inflammatory and analgesic, and is a restoration of proprioception. The return to the training is recommended after 8-10 weeks. (www.carolina.pl), (www.medisa.pl), (www.ortopeda.zdrowemiasto.pl). Both at the sportsmen starting football as well as at those training handball, the most frequent micro injuries are contusions and musculo-tendinous unit injuries.

Muscular contusions belong to a group of closed injuries and are the consequence of the fall of competitor on the hard surface. They can also occur as a result of the direct action of an injury, which leads to hemorrhage to the muscle. As a result, the darkening of the skin appears, commonly described as a bruise. The temperature of the contusion area is higher, the pain is present, and scar tissue may also build up in the extravasated blood area, which partially reduces myocardial contractility and endurance. (Krämer 1997), (Tylman, Dziak 1996).

The initial goal of the treatment is to inhibit bleeding by applying cold, pressing the damaged area and by elevation of the limb above the level of the chest. Any kind of warming up, massage of the contusion area, or the continuation of physical activity are absolutely inadvisable. They may exacerbate bleeding, and enlarge hematoma, which in turn can lead to serious complications. (Krämer 1997), (Trzaska 2002). Sometimes, as a result of deep muscle contusions, fascial compartment syndrome occurs in a particular muscle group leading to the outbreak of ossifying muscle inflammation (myositis ossificans).

The injury to the musculo-tendinous unit is defined as damage in the area of attachment of muscle belly, muscle, tendon or attachment. This condition may be the result of overload (then we are dealing with chronic trauma) or individual overload case (then we are talking about acute injury). Severe damage to the musculo-tendinous unit is taking place at the certain height of the unit. The weakest element is usually damaged when the violent force is used. Depending on its value, the resistance of tissues to which this force acts, the following three level scale can be proposed (Kuś 1984):

Damage I ° - light (strain). It is a benign lesion, rarely painful. Such damage is not responsible for the loss of force or restriction of mobility. Treatment of acute symptoms is to protect the muscle from the active muscle contraction and passive stretching. Leg is lifted, or simply immobilized. Recovery is fast.

Damage II° - moderate (tear). In this case there is damage to the impaired extremity dexterity and strength. The continuity of the whole chain is verified by means of palpation, but you can not specify exactly how many fibers of musculo-tendinous unit was broken. In most cases, the only treatment is immobilization of the limb in a cast.

Damage III - severe (complete tear). These injuries occur not only by exerting of the large force against resistance, but also as a result of ignoring the recommendations of the physician, and following the transition from II ° to III °. Interruption leads to a complete separation of the muscle, muscle from the tendon or tendon from the bone. The characteristic symptom is intense pain, accompanied by severe muscle spasm, swelling or bruising with hematoma. Treatment consists of surgical restoration of the continuity of musculo-tendinous unit. Chronic damage to the musculo-fibrous bodies may be the result of long term overload, initiated by acute trauma. The consequence of its occurrence is to call an inflammatory response which, in its turn, causes the muscle contraction. Therapeutic treatment is to protect against subsequent injury, and rest. Symptoms of pain may be relieved by topical application of heat, but the role of prevention is much more important to the outcome than the treatment itself. (Kuś 1984).

Aim

The purpose of this study was to illustrate the most common types of injuries which both men who train football and handball are subjected to.

Material and methods

The research material was a group of 60 people aged from 18 years to 38 years practising team games. [Table 1].

Table 1. The figures and percentages for the ages of the players.

GROUP	AGE	Number of players			
		Football		Handball	
		n	%	n	%
I	18-24 lat	15	50	10	33,3
II	25-31 lat	10	33,3	17	56,7
III	32-38 lat	5	16,7	3	10
Total		30	100	30	100

The research was conducted on a given day in 2009 and 2010 on the sports facilities in the cities, where both teams trained. Respondent men belonged to clubs where they train and fight out the matches: A group of GSE k15 Krosno football players and a group of handball players from the team GKS Grunwald Ruda Śląska. Subjects represented the highest level of sports, and were divided into two groups.

The first group consisted of people training football (30 players), between the ages of 18 to 38 years. Practice ranged from 6 to 10 years, training 2 to 5 times a week 1.5 hours a time dimension. [Table 2, 3].

Table 2 The figures and percentages of the football players' practice.

PRACTICE	n	%
3 years	2	6,7
6 years	5	16,7
8 years	4	13,3
9 years	2	6,7
10 years	5	16,7
11 years	4	13,3
15 years	3	10
16 years	2	6,7
17 years	1	3,3
21 years	1	3,3
23 years	1	3,3
Total	30	100

Table 3 The frequency of workouts per week (figures and percentages.)

NUMBER OF FOOTBALL TRAININGS WEEKLY	NUMBER OF ATHLETES	
	n	%
1 times a week	3	10
2 times a week	8	26,7
3 times a week	3	10

4 times a week	7	23,3
5 times a week	7	23,3
6 times a week	2	6,7
TOTAL	30	100

The second group training handball, was represented by 30 athletes. Age of respondents in this discipline was also 18 to 38 years, and their seniority ranged from 10 to 16 years. Subjects trained every week from 3 to 7 times, and the training time was 1.5 hours each time. [Table 4, 5].

Table 4 The figures and percentages of handball players' practice.

<i>PRACTICE</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>%</i>
11 years	1	3,3
12 years	15	50
13 years	5	16,7
15 years	8	26,7
16 years	1	3,3
TOTAL	30	100

Table 5 The frequency of workouts per week (figures and percentages.)

<i>NUMBER OF HANDBALL TRAININGS WEEK</i>	<i>NUMBER OF ATHLETES</i>	
	<i>n</i>	<i>%</i>
1 time a week	-	-
2 times a week	-	-
3 times a week	4	13,3
4 times a week	20	66,7
5 times a week	4	13,3
7 times a week	2	6,7
TOTAL	30	100

To obtain the test material, a specially prepared questionnaire for this work was developed by the author. The survey consisted of open questions, half-open questions and multiple choice questions. In the first part the specification containing the demographic data relating to the players was placed, as well as the type of team sport, training period and the amount of training per week.

In the survey questionnaire detailed questions were also included, about the type of injuries covered in the lower limbs, their causes, duration of treatment and absence from training, which involves a return to health, or its lack. So the survey developed that way, and relating to the trauma involved in practicing sports of football and handball, made it possible to evaluate the risk of many injuries. Responses were categorized by respondents, while the figures and percentages were placed in tables. Participation in the study was completely voluntary and anonymous, and selection of people was random.

Results

Based on the analysis of data obtained from a questionnaire survey conducted among 60 men doing sports, in football, trauma succumbed to all the respondents, i.e. 30 players. In handball 28 people had lower limb injuries, which constituted 93.3% of those researched, and

two players (6.7%) responded, that they had not yet had an injury in their sports career. The study shows, that both the players in football, as well as those who played handball in equal measure are exposed to, and undergo numerous injuries, while playing sports activities, whether during training or matches [Table 6].

Table 6. The occurrence of injuries in football players and handball.

<i>PRESENCE OF INJURY</i>	NUMBER OF ATHLETES			
	Handball		Football	
	n	%	n	%
Yes	30	100	28	93,3
No	-	-	2	6,7
Total(n/%)	30	100	30	100

Table 7. The location and type of injuries of lower extremities in football players and their numerical and percentage distribution.

LOWER LIMB				
<i>LOCATION OF INJURY</i>	TYPE OF INJURY	NUMBER OF INJURIES		TOTAL %
		n	%	
Knee joint	contusion	3	7,5	57,5
	twist	3	7,5	
	subluxation	-	-	
	dislocation	4	10	
ligamentous apparatus damage	collateral ligaments	2	5	30
	cruciate ligaments	6	15	
	anterior cruciate ligament injury	2	5	
	kneecap injury	3	7,5	
ankle joint and foot joints	contusion	7	17,5	30
	twist	4	10	
	subluxation	-	-	
	dislocation	1	2,5	
damage Achilles tendon injury	rupture	-	-	2,5
	partial	1	2,5	
damaging the bone	cracks	-	-	10
	fractures	4	10	

TOTAL (n/%)		42	100	100
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Table 8 The location and type of lower limb injuries in handball players and their numerical and percentage distribution.

LOWER LIMB				
<i>LOCATION OF INJURY</i>	TYPE OF INJURY	NUMBER OF INJURIES		TOTAL %
		n	%	
Knee joint	contusion	2	5,7	42,9
	twist	4	11,4	
	subluxation	-	-	
	dislocation	2	5,7	
ligamentous apparatus damage	collateral ligaments	1	2,9	42,9
	cruciate ligaments	2	5,7	
	anterior cruciate ligament injury	3	8,6	
	kneecap injury	1	2,9	
ankle joint and foot joints	contusion	-	-	51,3
	twist	13	37	
	subluxation	-	-	
	dislocation	5	14,3	
damage Achilles tendon injury	rupture	1	2,9	2,9
	partial	-	-	
damaging the bone	cracks	-	-	2,9
	fractures	1	2,9	
TOTAL (n/%)		36		100

Table 7 and 8 is a statement of figures and percentages of the most common injuries of lower extremities in people practicing football and handball, and their specific location. 51.3% of all respondents practicing handball reported, that the most vulnerable to injury was the ankle joint. The most common injury, which occurred in the thirteen subjects and constituted 37% of cases, was ankle sprain, as well as the dislocation in five cases, which accounted for 14.3%. The second place in terms of frequency of injury, as described by the handball players, was a knee joint with 42.9% of cases. The players experienced a number of twists here 11.4% (four people), three (8.6%) suffered damage to the meniscus, and in two patients (5.7%) anterior cruciate ligament has been broken. Discussed above injuries and their location were the most frequently mentioned by the interviewed persons, and accounted for 94.2% of the most frequently occurring leg injuries that occur while playing handball. It can be deduced from the data obtained, that the smallest percentage i.e. 5, 8% were following injuries, such as Achilles tendon rupture and fracture of great toe in two

players (2.9%). At football, the biggest number of injuries related to changes within the knee joint, 57.5%, and the ankle joint, 30%. Four patients sustained injury to the anterior cruciate ligament, and two to the posterior cruciate ligament. Respondents indicated that the second, a very common injury to the knee joint is dislocation. According to the survey questionnaire, 10% or four players suffered from this type of injury. Four respondents (10%) reported damage to the meniscus and tibial ligament. Other injuries are numerous injuries to the bone (including fractures), and damage to the knee-cap (17.5%). The largest group of ankle injuries were severe contusions (17.5%) in seven respondents. In four (10%) the sprain occurred, and partial rupture of the Achilles tendon involved only one person. There are many components which contribute to the occurrence of injuries. This is a very important aspect that allows us to see what the pathomechanisms of their incidence are. For both handball and football as a major mechanism leading to injury, athletes indicated the quality of enabling full contact at sport - 83.3% when it comes to handball, and 63.3% for football. Improperly performed warm-up was the second frequently mentioned as a response in 20% and 10% of players handball. 6.7% of the handball players felt that not healed injuries lead to even worse injury, as in the case of football was 10%. The results are summarized below [Table 9].

Table 9 Causes of injuries in football and handball (percentages and numbers)

MECHANISM OF INJURY	NUMBER OF ATHLETES			
	FOOTBALL		HANDBALL	
	n	%	n	%
contact nature of sport	19	63,3	25	83,3
Improper warm-up	6	20	3	10
Overtraining	2	6,7	-	-
Unhealed injuries	3	10	2	6,7
Unhealed injuries	-	-	-	-
TOTAL	30	100	30	100

Table 10 shows the length of absence from training in athletes with a history of trauma. The most common answer given for both handball and football players was that the interval between the training was a month. This was indicated by nine people representing 30% of football players, and twenty-two of those playing handball, which accounted for 73.3%. Three people (10%) practicing handball indicated that a period of not doing sport after the injury was three months, and seven people (23.3%) practicing football said that their absence from training was for six months. Two handball players (6.7%) and one football player (3.4%) did not take an active part in physical activity for over a year.

Table 10 The percentages and figures for the time gaps in training after the injury.

BREAK IN TRAINING TIME	NUMBER OF ATHLETES			
	football		handball	
	n	%	n	%
12 months	4	13,3	2	6,7
6 months	7	23,3	1	3,3
1 month	9	30	22	73,3
3 months	5	16,7	3	10
Over a year	1	3,4	2	6,7
No answer	4	13,3	-	-
TOTAL(n/%)	30	100	30	100

The players of both team games, answered that the most common micro-injury while

practising sport were contusions - 56.7% with handball players, and 46.7% - with the football players. There were also frequent cases of the soft tissue stretching. This happened to seven football players at the percentage of 23.3%, and nine handball players - 30% of cases. Next micro-injuries coming in fairly large numbers were wounds which were recorded with the three handball players (10%), and tear injuries with six football players (20%). The results discussed are illustrated in Table No. 11.

Table 11. The percentages and figures on micro-injuries with football and handball players during training.

TYPE OF MICRO-INJURY	ELEMENT BEING EXAMINED			
	Football		Handball	
	n	%	n	%
contusions	14	46,7	17	56,7
strains	7	23,3	9	30
tears	6	20	1	3,3
Injures/wounds	3	20	3	10
other	-	-	-	-
TOTAL	30	100	30	100

To the question, whether they used rehabilitation during treatment, more than half of those surveyed, which was 53.3%, answered in the affirmative, and 46.7% responded with denial. Football players were those, who used rehabilitation more often, there were 20 cases, which accounted for 66.7% of cases. With handball players these numbers were 12 and 40% of cases, respectively. More than a half of handball players - sixteen people (57%), did not participate in rehabilitation after trauma at all.

Among the wide range of physiotherapy treatments, respondents most often mentioned magnetic field and laser (25%), ultrasound and cryotherapy were in the second place (15%). In the case of handball players five people indicated having undergone cryotherapy (47.1%), four persons representing 33.3% indicated the laser, and the two people (16.7%) benefited from the magnetotherapy. However, from the kinesitherapy area, only four football players indicated gymnastics. None of the respondents playing handball gave such a response.

Table 12. Type of procedures performed after trauma.

TYPE TREATMENT USED	ELEMENT EXAMINED			
	Football		Handball	
	n	%	n	%
laser	5	25	4	16,7
magnetotherapy	5	25	2	33,3
ultrasound	3	15	1	8,3
cryotherapy	3	15	5	41,7

gymnastics	4	20	-	-
TOTAL	20	100	12	100

Out of the respondents asked whether they used the orthopedic / rehabilitation equipment, 50% replied in the affirmative. The data analysis showed, that the persons benefiting from rehabilitation equipment most often (in the twelve cases) used the elbow-crutch constituting 60% of the whole for football players, and five people (50%) in the case of handball players. Frequently mentioned were all kinds of bands, orthopedic - 20% in football players, and 30% in handball players. In the case of the injury within the knee, a stabilizer of the knee proved to be the necessary rehabilitation equipment. Three football players (15%) and two handball players (20%) came back to health with the use of it. In the case of one person doing football (5%), a wheelchair has been used.

Table 13 The type of orthopedic rehabilitation equipment.

TYPE OF REHABILITATION EQUIPMENT	ELEMENT EXAMINED			
	Football		Handball	
	n	%	n	%
stabilizer	3	15	2	20
Elbow crutch	12	60	5	50
Orthopedic bands	4	20	3	30
wheelchair	1	5	-	-
TOTAL	20	100	10	100

The vast majority of respondents, i.e. 71.9% of athletes found, that a after the rehabilitation and following the trauma after the accident, they did not return to such a state of health as before the injury.

Table 14 .Type of reported symptoms occurring in people whose health did not return to pre-injury state.

TYPE OF AILMENTS PRESENT	NUMBER OF ATHLETES			
	Football		Handball	
	n	%	n	%
trauma	1	7,7	-	-
Limitation of joint load	4	30,8	2	20
pain	5	38,5	3	30
Limitation of joint mobility	3	23	5	50
TOTAL (n/%)	13	100	10	100

With both football and handball players, there are numerous problems after trauma endured. Football players most often - four people - complained of the pain (38.5%). Three people, or 23%, complained of restricted mobility in the joint. Handball players, after trauma endured, mostly complained about the limitation of movement in the joint. This was in the case of five people (50%). There were also complaints relating to severe pain that occurred during physical activity.

Three respondents representing 30% pointed at that.

Overview

Active participation in sporting activities entails the incidence of numerous contusions, injuries, which result in the lesion also described as sport trauma. This also applies to team sports, such as football and handball. Even the experienced sportsmen with the long history of actually doing certain discipline can't really avoid sustaining injuries from time to time. This is to conclude from the present work, where 96.7% of the persons being examined confirmed having sustained injuries in the past. After looking closely at the responses to the survey queries, we see that there were only two persons doing handball, who had never experienced injuries. They were the youngest, belonging to the first age group (18-24 years) with the average age of 21. We can only speculate whether their playing down on the problem may be attributed to their ignorance as to the real symptoms resulting from the very young age, or to the lack of proper medical care. As we know, the nature of the injury as to its scale, may be diverse, from light to very grave, which require surgical intervention and long recovery.

Following the research, we can state that the most frequent injuries as to their place of occurrence were foot injuries (51.3%), mainly ankle joint distortion (37%) and its sprain (14.3%). Such injuries cause the biggest damage to the joint ligaments, because its proper treatment is often ignored, if only neglected, especially with the youngest and thus the most active age group, where the damage to the ankle joint is the most common. Leanderson confirms, that 13-56% of all sport injuries relate to the ankle joint. Restrom puts forward that 31% of all injuries at handball are those of the ankle joint (Widuchowski, Franiel, Widuchowski 2005). We learn from the research which was carried out, that the second place as to the localization of the injuries with the handball players is occupied by the knee joint (42.9%). As to the localization of the most frequent injuries with the football players, the situation seems to be completely opposite to that of handball players.

It can be assumed from the results of the research, that at football, the most vulnerable joint was knee joint (57.5%). The damage occurred to both anterior and posterior cruciate ligaments. Also knee joint sprains were present. With the ankle joint, many strong contusions (17.5%) and distortions (10%) were noted. Many micro-injuries occur, both during matches and training sessions, because of the contact nature of the sport. Among all the persons being researched, 46.7% of football and 56.7% of handball players indicated joint contusions, while responding to the survey. The absence from the training period time with 42% persons being researched was shorter than the usual time necessary for the full recovery after the accident, which might mean, that those being surveyed were physically active and participated in the training activities regardless of the not fully healed injuries.

Conclusions

- Distortions and sprains of the joint together with the damage to the knee ligaments were characteristic injuries in sport disciplines being examined, and the most frequent places where they appeared were foot and knee (ankle and knee joint).
- In most cases, the contact nature of these sports was the patho-mechanism of these injuries.
- The absence from training with the majority of those being researched was approximately 1 month, and for the anterior cruciate ligaments tear and for the partial Achilles tendon tear it might have lasted even for 6 months.
- The most frequent micro-injuries that occur during training are numerous contusions, sprains and tears.

Literature

- Adamczyk G.(2005). Urazy w piłce nożnej, Forum trenera, 1, s.171-175.
- Andrzejewski T., Trytek- Piskiewicz A.(2004). Fizjoterapia Polska,(4)4,s.331-336.
- Brown D. E.(2006).Sekrety ortopedii, w: Urban & Partner.
- Frańczuk B.i wsp.(2004). Wczesna rehabilitacja po artroskopowej rekonstrukcji więzadła krzyżowego przedniego, Ortopedia Traumatologia Rehabilitacja, (6)4, s. 416- 422.
- Górecki A.(1997).Uszkodzenia stawu kolanowego, PZWL , Warszawa.
- Heim U., Baltensweiler M.(1995). Kompendium traumatologii, PZWL, Warszawa.
- Krämer J., Ortopedia, Springer PWN, Warszawa 1997;

Kuś W. M., Urazowe uszkodzenia kolana, PZWL Warszawa 1984,s.61-67,130-132;
Milewska M., Mańka J.(2002).Propozycja programu usprawniania po rekonstrukcji więzadła krzyżowego tylnego stawu klanowego z użycie autoprzeszczepu ze ścięgna m. prostego uda, *Medicina Sportiva*, 6, s.67-79.
Mędraś M.(2004).*Medycyna sportowa*, MEDSPORTPRESS, Warszawa.
Pasierbiński A., Jarząbek A.(2002).Rehabilitacja po rekonstrukcji więzadła krzyżowego przedniego, *Medicina Sportiva* ,6, s. 51-65;
Paterka S.(2001).Piłka ręczna,1, AWF Poznań.
Trzaska T.(2002).aktualne metody rekonstrukcji więzadeł krzyżowych kolana, *Medicina Sportiva* , 6, s. 19-22.
Tylman D., Dziak A.(1996).*Traumatologia narządu ruchu. Tom II*, w: PZWL Warszawa,s.206-264.
Widuchowski J. Franiel J., Widuchowski W.(2005).Ostre obrażenia stawu skokowo-goleniowego u sportowców,w: *Chirurgia kolana, artroskopia, traumatologia Sportowa*,(2) 3, s. 51-61.
Widuchowski J., Grzywocz J.(1996).Ocena urazowości wśród piłkarzy I, II, III ligi w sezonie 1994/95. *Medycyna Sportowa*.
www.carolina.pl;
www.kulturystka.magicsport.pl
www.medisa.pl
www.onlyfutbol.pl
www.ortopeda.zdrowemiasto.pl